

Towards a Portfolio Approach: Partnerships for Sustainable Transformations

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Abstract

This perspective article examines the role that partnerships can play in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It elucidates a portfolio approach to partnerships that could align well with achieving a sustainable transformation. To conclude, it outlines recommendations on how this approach may be operationalized in research, policy, and practice. Much remains to be done on a portfolio approach. Practice and sharing of good practice should be guiding principles to facilitate peer-to-peer learning. It is also important to address power imbalances, conflicting interests, and limited representation in partnerships.

1 | SUSTAINABLE TRANSFORMATIONS

The COVID-19 crisis and its impact in low and middle-income countries has highlighted the importance of the UN Secretary General's call for a Decade of Action on the Sustainable Development (SDGs) centered around an inclusive multilateralism (Klingebiel & Gonsior, 2020; Sachs et al., 2021; UN, 2019a, 2021; UN SG Report, 2021). To facilitate such an approach, the UN Development Reforms have aligned the development sector with the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs. At the core of the reforms is the Sustainable Development Cooperation Framework (SDCF) which seeks to improve coordination within the broader multilateral system and to better align multilateral efforts with National Development Plans (UN, 2019b).

To make meaningful progress on the SDGs, the SDCF will need to support sustainable transformations in a range of systems: health, education, agriculture and land-use, energy and industry, urban infrastructure, and digital revolution (Sachs, 2019; Sachs et al., 2019; TWI, 2050, 2018; UN GSDR, 2019). However,

questions remain on how cooperation frameworks such as this can best support systems transformations of this kind (Chan et al., 2021; Klingebiel & Gonsior, 2020). First, the transformations need to be designed for, adapted to regional and national contexts, and reflected in National Development Plans (Sachs et al., 2019). Ultimately, each country must choose its own path. Consequently, cooperation frameworks should seek to complement state-centered approaches to transformation. Second, no country can single-handedly deliver all the transformations. Transnational cooperation mechanisms are needed to harness resources and capabilities from diverse sources such as sustainable finance, technology and know-how, policy expertise and data, and other capacities (Akram, 2021). Third, achieving specific transformations, such as energy decarbonization, sustainable agriculture or digital transformation (Sachs et al., 2019; UN GSDR, 2019), require a broad range of responses from different sectors and levels of society, yet, societies lack many of the appropriate institutions, policies and societal responses to effectively mobilize multisectoral approaches to transformation and engage an array

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of stakeholders as equal partners (Beck et al., 2021; Devaney & Torney, 2018).

In particular, partnerships that bring together global, regional, national and local actors from multiple sectors of society appear necessary to realize these transformations. Owing to the geographic concentration of knowledge, finance, innovation, and production, and the need to develop and diffuse sustainable technologies, institutions, and practices globally (Ciarli et al., 2021; Malecki, 2021; TWI 2050, 2019; Walsh et al., 2020) and to engage local communities and stakeholders in the process of transformation (Elstub et al., 2021; TWI 2050, 2020), this perspective article proposes constructing coherent portfolios of partnerships for each country and ways to operationalize a portfolio approach to sustainable transformations in the context of the recent UN reforms in the multilateral development system.

2 | THREE ROLES FOR PARTNERSHIPS

It is common in the sustainable development literature to define partnerships as voluntary collaborations among multiple stakeholders (Hujistee & Francken, 2007; Pattberg et al., 2012). However, for the purposes of sustainable transformation, a focus on multi-stakeholder partnerships to the exclusion of other types of partnerships appears much too narrow. Indeed, the 2030 Agenda offers a broader understanding of the forms of partnerships required: a revitalized global partnership (Target 17.16) complemented by various types of partnerships – public, public-private, civil society (Target 17.17). In this paper, I use a broad definition of partnerships encompassing many types of collaborative arrangements that can support sustainable transformations, including multi-stakeholder partnerships, public-private partnerships, geo-political partnerships, peace accords, social partnerships, informal diaspora alliances, and sponsorships by philanthropists. At a basic level, such partnerships must comprise three main elements: actors, a collaborative function, and a sustainable development goal.

Several scholars have emphasized the contribution that partnerships (variously construed) can play in delivering sustainable transformations, such as multi-stakeholder partnerships in energy decarbonization (Westman & Castán Broto, 2018), public-private partnerships for digital transformation (Sachs, 2019) and geo-political partnerships to pursue green transition (Denton et al., 2021). However, the different literatures that advocate for partnerships tend to emphasize different roles for partnerships. In what follows, I focus on three of these: to complement state-centered approaches, to harness the means of implementation (MOIs), and to achieve an integrated approach.

First, as recognized in the climate governance literature, partnerships can complement and even stimulate

government-centered approaches to transformation (Andonova et al., 2017; Chan et al., 2021; Green, 2013; Hale, 2016; Hoffman, 2011). A crucial role of partnerships is their combined contribution to goal attainment which can help to 'bridge the ambition gap' left by weak government commitments, resources, or capabilities (Blok et al., 2012; Chan et al., 2018; Lui et al., 2020). For example, to quantify cooperative initiatives aggregate emissions reduction potential, Lui et al. (2020) developed a methodology to estimate the impact of 17 transnational climate initiatives involving cities, businesses, and regions. Their analysis suggests that these initiatives could reduce emissions by 18–21 GtCO₂e/year (compared to current national policies total contribution of 60–63 GtCO₂e/year).

Second, partnerships are an important mechanism to harness the MOIs. This role is strongly emphasized in the official UN documents (UN, 2015). In a seminal academic paper on this issue, Westman and Castán Broto (2018) analyzed a database containing 72 climate partnerships in 15 Chinese cities involving city authorities, companies, local academia, and NGOs. Their findings indicate partnerships performed a range of functions in support of energy decarbonization including facilitating technology development and low-carbon demonstration projects, standard setting and public infrastructure provision, technology transfer, and enhancing access to finance and markets for local climate action (Westman & Castán Broto, 2018).

Third, as highlighted in the SDG implementation literature, partnerships are needed to achieve an integrated approach (Horan, 2019a; Hujistee et al., 2007; Le Blanc, 2015; Nilsson & Griggs, 2016; Stafford-Smith et al., 2016; Weitz et al., 2017). In particular, they offer an institutional arrangement to manage interlinkages and interactions between multiple SDGs. By bringing together key actors from interconnected sectors (water, energy, health, etc.) and stakeholder groups (government, UN agencies, business, academic, NGOs), partnerships can help to exploit synergies and tackle trade-offs and thereby enable more effective *and* equitable implementation (Horan, forthcoming). In other words, partnerships can help to ensure the voices of stakeholders are heard (Pattberg & Widerberg, 2016) and therefore forge a more coordinated multisectoral approach to transformation. Moreover, partnerships are seen as vehicles to address participation and representation deficits in sustainability governance and as a way to raise the legitimacy of efforts to address sustainability challenges (Backstrand, 2006; Backstrand & Kuyper, 2017; Haas, 2004).

Overall, partnerships are a highly flexible vehicle to bring together key actors to tackle specific challenges in the path to transformation. However, to enable an effective and legitimate partnership approach to sustainable transformations, key challenges are the identification of relevant partnerships, the functions to perform, and the actors to engage, as well as the

institutions and policies to support them. In addition, questions remain on the extent to which partnerships are additional to or substitute for policies and actions elsewhere (Andonova et al., 2017; Horan, 2019b; Hsu et al., 2020; Lui et al., 2020).

2.1 | The need to balance the three roles

The case of Ireland's Celtic Tiger from the mid-1990s to 2008 illustrates the positive contribution a variety of partnerships can make to a country's development and the importance of balancing the three roles of partnerships in the more challenging context of sustainable transformations.

Ireland's growth miracle depended strongly on outside influences for its realization, however, most explanations focus on the mix of national policies (see Table 1). For example, a low corporation tax rate, access to the European single market in combination with investments in infrastructure and higher education, as well as a competitive advantage from low relative wages and a peace agreement in Northern Ireland all helped to attract investment and technology.

While the importance of getting the policies right is irrefutable, less attention is given to the partnerships – transnational, regional, national, local – that created an environment in which the government's development policies were especially effective (O'Donnell, 1998).

For example, connections with the Irish diaspora in the USA were particularly important in bringing foreign direct investment (FDI) to Ireland. Similarly, membership of the European Union was crucial to provide access to the European Single Market and new sources of development finance and expertise. For example, a large portion of funds invested in infrastructure came from the EU Regional Development Fund. Moreover, investments in university facilities were sponsored by philanthropists both in Ireland and the USA, particularly

TABLE 1 Partnerships that supported Ireland's development (1990–2008).

Policies	Partnerships
Low corporation tax rate.	With diaspora community and business leaders in the USA.
Access to the European Single Market.	EU Membership (1973).
Investments in infrastructure and higher education institutions.	EU Regional Development Funds. Partnerships with philanthropists.
Low relative wages.	Social Partnership (1987–2008). Wage agreements between government and trade unions (O'Donnell, 2020, 2008).
Good Friday Agreement (1998).	Partnership across communities brokered by governments.

in universities linked to high-technology industries. The social partnership between government, the main employer groups and the trade unions (1987–2008) considerably helped to tame wage growth throughout the period and to ensure industrial peace after a succession of strikes by state owned enterprises in the 1980s (O'Donnell, 1998, 2020). Finally, a peace agreement in Northern Ireland is inconceivable without prior agreement between the two communities to find peace that was brokered by the American, British, and Irish governments.

Though this portfolio of partnerships was arguably more incidental than deliberately orchestrated, it is clear from Table 1 that the portfolio consisted of a diverse mix of partnerships that combined to harness finance, capacity building, FDI and technology transfer. However, the assembled portfolio failed in many respects to achieve an integrated approach. For the most part, the partnerships themselves engaged little with vulnerable groups, national NGOs, the environmental sector, or local communities. Instead, the portfolio primarily reflected economic imperatives and a traditional growth model harnessing in many instances unsustainable MOIs.

3 | TOWARDS A PORTFOLIO OF PARTNERSHIPS FOR SUSTAINABLE TRANSFORMATIONS

Increasingly, scholars call for a portfolio approach to partnerships to achieve sustainable transformations (Horan, 2019a; Mazzucato, 2021; Moreno-Serna et al., 2020; Prescott & Stibbe, 2020). However, to use a portfolio approach, we need to think carefully about what mix of partnerships is needed (Horan, 2019a). How can a portfolio of partnerships and partners be constructed that creates the conditions to achieve multiple SDGs? Importantly, what portfolio would attract the finance, technologies, data, policy expertise and other capacities that could deliver a sustainable transformation?

3.1 | Identifying partnerships and partners

I propose that it is helpful to think in terms of two portfolios. First there is the *current portfolio*, that is, all partnerships which are currently in place. Often, this portfolio is unknown although it is potentially observable. Most governments keep a database of developments projects under management in its country. UN agencies have similar databases. Private companies also. In this sense, the current portfolio could be observed if these databases are joined together through for example data sharing agreements.

The second portfolio is what I call here the *target portfolio*. It is the set of partnerships that could deliver

a sustainable transformation. It requires research and deliberation to know what that portfolio should be. Tools and institutions could help to envisage such a portfolio.

If we did know this target portfolio, we could compare it to the current portfolio and ask are there any *missing partnerships*, who are the *missing partners*? How can any gaps be filled? Does this require a policy framework and cooperation with UN agencies to catalyze the missing partnerships and bring the missing partners on board?

3.2 | Governance mechanism

Such an approach elaborates on the orchestration-type frameworks proposed in the climate governance literature (Chan et al., 2015; Chan et al., 2018, 2021; Chan & Pauw, 2014; Hale, 2020). In particular, the portfolio approach is consistent with the four design principles proposed in Chan et al. (2021): to be comprehensive; to be evaluative; to be catalytic; and to be collaborative. The added-value of the approach is that it allows for the development of partnership portfolio management techniques that can help to direct actors to challenges where partnering would contribute most to achieving sustainable transformations.

To construct portfolios for achieving the SDGs, the UN Development Reforms, and in particular the Sustainable Development Cooperation Framework offer a unique opportunity to bring greater coherence to the entire system of partnerships for each country. To help developing countries acquire the capabilities to identify and structure partnerships for sustainable transformations, the nearly 200 country offices of the UN system can be used to bring together UN agencies, regional development banks, international NGOs, government ministries, domestic stakeholders, and local community representatives to orchestrate partnerships portfolios (Akram, 2021).

3.3 | The case of Africa and its transformation potential

Africa is an important case in the context of transformative cooperation frameworks because compared to other parts of the world, it does not have to the same extent, large infrastructures that can lock-in society to unsustainable pathways.

There is growing momentum in Africa for economic transformation and increasing realization that African countries need not follow unsustainable pathways (Denton et al., 2021; Rodrik, 2018; Sachs, 2019; UNCTAD, 2021). For example, all African countries signed the 2030 Agenda which calls for inclusive and sustainable economic development (UN, 2015). Green transition is embedded in Agenda 2063, the continent's

long-term development plan (AUC, 2015a, 2015b). Post-COVID-19 recovery plans such as the draft African Green Stimulus Programme offer a timely opportunity to direct development towards more sustainable pathways (UNEP, 2021).

However, in the struggle to develop it is tempting for policymakers and planners to make decisions in the early stages with long-term unsustainable consequences (Unruh, 2000, 2002). Prominent examples are investments in energy and transportation infrastructure, key enablers of economic development, where carbon lock-in has had persistent negative effects for environment, society, and politics.

It is important for these countries and the multilateral system to recognize at the outset the potentially enormous advantages to developing after others (Davison et al., 2000; Sachs, 2019), and the need for coherent systems of partnerships to actualize these benefits (Denton et al., 2021; Radosevic et al., 2019; TWI 2050, 2020). In principle, it is possible to leapfrog by transferring sustainable technologies and institutions from other countries (Bajpai & Biberman, 2021; Curato et al., 2021). It is also possible to lock-in more sustainable social practices in, for example, transport through the adoption of sustainable modes of transport in use elsewhere. The transfer and deployment of digital technologies can facilitate the growth of entirely new industries and more inclusive institutions and societies (Sachs, 2019; TWI 2050, 2019).

In what follows, I first outline two methodological approaches based on roadmaps and linkages that can help to respectively identify strategic partnerships and key partners. I then tackle the question of how to orchestrate these partnerships.

4 | PROBING THE TARGET PORTFOLIO FOR ENERGY SYSTEMS TRANSFORMATION

While Horan (2019a) did not address international development, it did probe characteristics of a target portfolio for decarbonization of power generation in advanced countries. It is conceivable many of these partnerships should also be adapted to low and middle-income countries for low-carbon development and therefore form part of the target portfolio for energy system transformations in these countries.

4.1 | Roadmap approach

To get a sense of what partnerships might be needed, technology roadmaps and long-term policy pathways can be useful tools for framing investigation and discussion of forms of partnerships needed. For instance, roadmaps help to give a sense of what problems in the transition pathway may require a partnership approach

and what functions the different partnerships should perform (Horan, 2019a).

Using SDSN's technology roadmap for energy decarbonization (SDSN & FEEM, 2019) and based on scattered examples of relevant partnerships, Horan (2019a) identified five examples of partnerships that should perhaps be in a transformative portfolio. Side-stepping the issue of how these partnerships performed in practice, attention focused instead on what the partnerships tried to achieve and where they might fit in a portfolio for the achievement of transformative progress.

The selection of partnerships focused on functions such as agenda setting, retraining, technology phase-out, capacity building, and technology development and transfer. The approach sought to map proposed partnerships to SDSN's roadmap to highlight their potential role in facilitating a low-carbon transition.

4.2 | What mix of partnerships might be needed?

Table 2 presents the five partnerships of Horan (2019a) that could together contribute to initiate, smooth, and accelerate energy decarbonization.

First, the Dutch Energy Agreement brought together stakeholders from government, the private sector and civil society to envision a low-carbon pathway for decarbonization. This type of partnership is particularly important for agenda setting at the outset and for getting buy-in from various sections of society. Second, the Just Transition Fund (JTF), an example from the USA, sought to work with local coalmining communities to retrain and reskill workers for the green economy. Partnerships such as this, which are being replicated in other countries, seem crucial to allay political opposition to policy changes in support of decarbonization. Third, the German Coal Exit Commission aims to gradually phase-out coal in a cost-effective manner and thus smooth the path to decarbonization.

Each of these examples point to national-level partnerships involving national and local-level organizations that could be important for facilitating decarbonization.

The latter two partnerships are international in some participating partners and focus on accelerating the

transformation. First, the Nordic transmission grid is an example of a partnership between three governments to share cross-border transmission network to help address intermittency problems with renewables (hydro in this case). The international solar alliance brings together leaders in advancing solar technology to reduce the cost of finance, the cost of the technology, and build relevant infrastructure, thus contributing to technology development, capacity building and technology transfer.

These are just some examples of types of partnerships that might be relevant. Together, they elucidate that a transformative portfolio will require a mix of partnerships, addressing different problems and performing different functions. Such a portfolio should operate on different stages of the transformation pathway and involve partnerships operating at global, regional, national, and local levels.

However, other partnerships also seem relevant. For instance, from a leapfrogging perspective, partnerships with international sustainability leaders and technology companies could facilitate faster adoption and transfer of sustainable technologies and institutions. 'Twinning' partnerships with universities in Asia and Europe to train home students to Master and PhD level can facilitate skill formation, cross-border knowledge dissemination, transnational network building and act as conduits to transfer advanced thinking in sustainability to developing countries. While examples of such partnerships exist (see e.g., the New Colombo Plan (Australia) and Norway Pacific Ocean Climate Scholarship Programme), they should arguably be rolled out at all universities that prioritize sustainable education and research. Students who stay in the West or Asia enlarge diaspora communities and connections with sustainability leaders and companies. This creates opportunities for cross-border flows of green knowledge, technology and business. While returnees bring home new knowledge and skills to utilize and impart to others.

The examples given are suggestive. As the blanks in Table 2 indicate, more systematic methods to identify the full range of partnerships in the target portfolio should be developed. Each partnership's role in the transformation and the functions to perform need to be clearly articulated. Performed functions should be

TABLE 2 Probing the target portfolio for energy: what mix of partnerships might be needed?

Stages of transformations	Partnerships for energy decarbonization (Horan, 2019a)	Partnerships for leapfrogging (?)
Initiate	Dutch Energy Agreement	Partnerships with international leaders in sustainability to access technology, new institutions and finance
	Just Transition Fund	Partnerships for educating and skilling up green workers
Smooth	German Coal Exit Commission	Others?
Accelerate	Nordic transmission grid	?
	International Solar Alliance	?

evaluated against agreed pathways. Relevancy is best determined based on whether these functions address specific challenges associated with a pathways implementation (Horan, 2019a).

4.3 | Identifying relevant partners

The singular focus of the roadmap approach on decarbonization and the technologies which underpin it is less useful for identifying actors to engage in partnerships. This is because of the limited attention the approach gives to synergies and trade-offs with other SDGs.

The literature on sustainability partnerships emphasizes that broad stakeholder participation is important for the effectiveness and legitimacy of partnerships (Backstrand & Kuyper, 2017; Pattberg & Widerberg, 2016). However, there is a lack of evidence-based tools to systematically identify relevant actors as well as institutions and policy frameworks to engage them in partnerships where their participation is absent.

In this paper, I consider relevancy to mean those actors whose participation in partnerships can help to promote synergies and manage trade-offs across multiple SDGs, thereby contributing to effective *and* equitable transformations. Such an approach is important to ensure greater coherence in sustainable development (Chan & Iacobuta, 2020). It also offers a lens through which to examine the political economy of SDG implementation (Horan, forthcoming).

4.4 | Linkages approach

To identify relevant actor constellations, one approach could use mappings of interlinkages between the SDGs and studies of the actor's alignment to specific goals and targets (Horan, forthcoming).

Comparing the two would offer information useful to assess the extent to which current constellations achieve an appropriate level of integration in partnerships. While the approach is data intensive, being predicated on having good knowledge of SDG interactions and actors' activities, and actual integration is by no means guaranteed, it does offer a strategic framework to identify those actors who are contributing to synergies and to trade-offs and to bring attention to important aspects of the political economy of implementation (Horan, 2021).

For instance, to facilitate energy decarbonization (SDG7), the Just Transition Fund (JTF) brings together coalmining communities aligned to upgrading industry (SDG9.4) and universities aligned to retraining workers for renewables (SDG4.7). From an SDG interactions perspective, the partnership combines two synergies between renewable energy expansion (SDG7.2) and

worker retraining (SDG4.7), and between renewable energy (SDG7.2) and technology upgrading of industry (SDG9.4) to help to alleviate trade-offs for communities reliant on fossil-fuel industries (SDG9.2). By implementing such a partnership, JTF can exploit these synergies, overcome an important political constraint to decarbonization and promote a just transition. In other words, the partnership appears to be well grounded in the logic of SDG interactions and therefore useful for achieving an integrated transformation.

Similarly, linkages between SDG7 and the other Goals and targets could help to assess the breadth of participation in the Dutch Energy Agreement. In this case, to effectively and legitimately set the agenda for low-carbon energy transition, the breath of participation should encompass all of the main stakeholders. In short, the absence of key stakeholders directly affected by SDG7 achievement may indicate important participation gaps.

Connecting SDG interactions with specific types of partnerships in this way has powerful potential because it provides an evidence-based framework and institutional arrangement to negotiate joint actions for integrated implementation (Le Blanc, 2015; Nilsson et al., 2016; Weitz et al., 2017). Furthermore, it offers a yardstick to assess participation and forge more effective and equitable partnerships (Horan, forthcoming).

Several scholars have called for methods to translate knowledge of SDG linkages into multi-sectoral collaborations for integrated implementation (Alcamo et al., 2020; Allen & Metternicht, 2021; Breuer & Janetschek, 2019; Nilsson et al., 2016). However, only a few such studies exist. For instance, Weitz et al. (2017) use network analysis to identify strongly interconnected SDG targets and on this basis, to identify relevant government ministries. Similar to the Dutch Energy example above, Horan (2020a) combines mappings of all first order SDG14 linkages and ministries' implementation responsibilities to develop concrete recommendations on which departments should cooperate for coherent SDG14 policymaking (Horan, 2020a, 2020b). While these contributions focus on partnerships for policy coordination across line ministries, the 'linkage approach' should be explored further and extended to include non-government societal stakeholders and other types of partnerships.

5 | ORCHESTRATING PARTNERSHIPS

Most countries lack formal frameworks to support partnerships for sustainable transformations (Beisheim & Simon, 2018). As a result, countries rely implicitly on bottom-up approaches to partnerships to achieve these transformations (Horan, 2019a).

Horan (2019a) provides evidence that a portfolio of partnerships aligned to sustainable transformation is unlikely to emerge in a bottom-up manner. In

addition, low participation from non-state and local actors in sustainability partnerships, such as universities, businesses, national and local governments, small NGOs and grassroot organizations has been a consistent finding across partnership database studies (Andonova & Levy, 2003; Pattberg et al., 2012; Westerwinter, 2021).

In short, in the absence of orchestration by states and UN agencies, that is, efforts to support and ensure partnerships (Hale, 2020; Hale & Roger, 2014), there are good reasons to believe missing partnerships and partners will arise. This provides a rationale and role for governments (supported by the multilateral system) to develop an enabling environment for transformation partnerships, orchestrate missing partnerships and incentivize the participation of relevant actors.

5.1 | Key recommendations

For each transformation (Sachs et al., 2019; UN GSDR, 2019), my main recommendations are,

1. To construct the current portfolio of partnerships through data sharing agreements.
2. To use roadmaps to build a shared vision of the partnerships needed and identify missing partnerships.
3. To use linkages to identify relevant partners and to assess missing actors to bring on board.
4. To close gaps, invest in infrastructure for partnerships, partnership brokers, skilled professionals to represent partners in collaborations and organization's capacity to partner.

The overarching goal should be to construct a country-specific, diverse and coherent portfolio of partnerships involving local, national, regional and international actors that is aligned to and capable of delivering a sustainable transformation.

6 | MEANS OF ORCHESTRATION

A range of means of orchestration can be used to support partnership portfolios. Literature in international relations, climate governance, and sustainability partnerships has documented multiple ways to steer public and private actors including ideational and material support, financial and other incentives, convening power and networks and learning processes (Abbot et al., 2012; Backstrand & Kuyper, 2017; Chan et al., 2021; Chan & Pauw, 2014; Widerberg, 2017). Rather than provide a survey of the different means (detailed surveys can be found in Abbot & Bernstein, 2015; Abbot et al., 2012; Abbott & Snidal, 2009; Hale & Rogers, 2014) and their relevance to partnership portfolio management, I will instead discuss two pertinent

approaches that receive less attention in these political science oriented literatures.

6.1 | Incentivizing participation through global funds, pooled financing and national funding schemes

First, an important challenge for partnering is often the lack of funding to do so. A UNDESA survey in 2016 of reports submitted by 79 partnerships registered in the Partnerships for SDGs Online Platform reported limited financial resources as the main obstacle to effective cross-sectoral partnering (UNDESA, 2016). Other challenges cited include turnover of staff, lack of human resources and infrastructure for partnering.

To enable 'missing' partnerships and to ensure the participation of 'missing' partners, new institutions and policy frameworks at global, regional, national, and subnational levels are likely needed. In what follows, I will focus on public funding schemes, although the private sector should also be seen as an important funding source for transformative cooperation frameworks.

Several global funds (e.g., GAVI, GEF) with considerable budgets fund multistakeholder initiatives and have a proven record of incentivizing participation in sustainable development projects (Sachs and Schmidt-Traub, 2017). Integrating into these funds a partnership portfolio approach could help to align many actors with sustainable transformations in low and middle-income countries. Second, it is widely recognized in UN circles that donor governments prioritize certain bilateral relationships with agencies, countries, and ministries. One problem with this approach is that it can lead to siloed and uncoordinated implementation. A mechanism should be found which pools such finance and places it at the disposal of transformative cooperation frameworks.

Despite the limited budgets of developing country governments, subsidy programs could still be established to support multi-sectoral partnerships. These may be particularly important for incentivizing participation of local stakeholders and could be supported by donors. While most schemes at national level focus on supporting intra-sectoral actors, such as startups, SMEs and university researchers, recent years have witnessed a large increase in programs to fund cross-sectoral partnering focused on addressing global challenges which may provide useful models for national level schemes aimed at shaping partnership portfolios.

Although many of these programs are relatively new (such as the EU Horizon 2020 Framework, IRC COALESCE scheme), future research should seek to examine appropriate incentive schemes to bring local stakeholders into partnerships and the challenges faced by these actors in cross-sectoral partnering.

6.2 | Partnerships platforms and the role of new technologies

Second, to achieve sustainable transformation, societies will need to shift to a more advanced multi-sectoral, multi-level cooperative approach. Up to now, the multi-lateral system has relied on rudimentary means to mobilize partnerships such as conferences and networks of lead actors (Beisheim & Simon, 2018). In addition, there is growing evidence of ‘Summit Fatigue’ (Chan et al., 2021).

New technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR) and Blockchain should be deployed to optimize cooperation frameworks for sustainability. This could bring international and transnational cooperation into a new era, however, the potential role of digital technologies in an advanced partnership approach has barely been examined (Del Río Castro et al., 2021).

For instance, AI and big data could be applied to develop an inventory of existing partnerships and to identify key missing partnerships to help construct a targeted partnership portfolio in each country. In addition, these technologies could be deployed to identify relevant partners, participation gaps, skills deficits, and inform actors of prospective partners, their partnering histories, and roles required to optimize collaborative performance. Furthermore, VR could help different stakeholder groups understand others’ experience and perspectives and thereby enhance trust and collaboration between diverse partners. AR could also be used to train representatives for partnering in advance of collaboration to ensure effective representation. Blockchain offers opportunities to maintain easily accessible records of actors’ participation, effectiveness, and past challenges.

Collaborative platforms that bring together different stakeholders are one avenue to operationalize and orchestrate a portfolio approach to transformations supported by digital technologies. It is recognized platforms can mobilize actors for collaborative projects (Ansell & Gash, 2018). While partnership platforms are growing in popularity, there remain few if any platforms capable of delivering transformative change (Prescott & Stibbe, 2020). In addition, these platforms do not make extensive use of the new technologies.

7 | CONCLUSIONS

When considering partnership's role in sustainable transformation, a portfolio approach is essential. UN discussions tend to focus on best practices in individual partnerships, examples of successful partnerships, and their challenges. Although these micro-level discussions are important and much research is devoted

to them (e.g., Leise & Beisheim, 2011; Mummery, 2021), the macro portfolio-level urgently requires attention.

In particular, research, policy, and practice should consider what portfolios of partnerships can deliver sustainable transformations. Roadmaps are useful tools to discern the types of partnerships needed. Linkages are a way to identify relevant actors to engage in these partnerships.

Supportive infrastructures and policy frameworks are also needed to facilitate a portfolio approach. Thus far, platforms to support partnerships are weakly institutionalized (Backstrand, 2006; Beisheim & Simon, 2018), and not systematic or well-developed from a portfolio perspective. Infrastructures to support SMEs, entrepreneurship and funding research are available in many countries. Similar scaffolding is required for sustainability partnerships.

Much remains to be done on a portfolio approach. Practice and sharing of good practice should be guiding principles to facilitate peer-to-peer learning. It is also important to address power imbalances, conflicting interests, and limited representation in partnerships. The study by Westerwinter (2021) provides a stark reminder that current patterns of participation are fragmented and lack representation from many stakeholder groups especially from national and local levels.

To achieve what UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres calls ‘inclusive and networked multilateralism’, and global sustainability transformations (Beisheim & Fritzsche, 2021; UN GSDR, 2019), these problems of partnerships should be put front and center, and ways found to address them.

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